

ANTITHESIS AND ITS INSTANCES IN LITERARY TEXTS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the analysis of the antithesis, its usage in the texts, distinct meaning as well as structural and semantic analysis based on the study of instances and excerpts of literature. The principal role of the antithesis, as a stylistic figure, is to implement concepts in a contrast. The article viewed concepts of scientists on the lexical-semantic concepts of the antithesis and presented examples from literary works and illustrated them in the article.

Keywords: Stylistics, negativity. stylistic devices, antithesis, semantics, contrast, opposition, irony, oxymoron, antonym.

Introduction

Antithesis is a complicated stylistic feature that serves a particular stylistic task in production. Studies show that age, one of the oldest stylistic styles, is extensively used in ultramodern Uzbek sensible speech styles. The main function of antibodies is distinction. The antithesis miracle emerges as a result of the stylistic use of speech units with a special syntactic structure grounded on semantic difference.

Method

Antithesis - (from the Greek- Antithesis - opposition) a stylistic pair figure in the text used for expressive-visual, humorous, ironic, evaluative and other purposes. The antithesis is almost always based on the parallelism of syntactic constructions. In the antithesis, two features are most often compared; for this, antonyms are mainly used - words with the opposing meaning: *Any sweetness has its own bitterness; each evil has its own goodness (Ralph Waldo Emerson)*. Using the antithesis enables us to express the main idea more obviously and emotionally, express our attitude more correctly to the expressed phenomena.

The antithesis is found not only in literature, but also in our everyday life, many things become clearer only when contrasting one with another: knowing grief, people value minutes of joy more. No wonder people say "Everything is known in comparison."

The same case happens to the pairs of "Heaven" and "the other way". In the text, they are presented as antonymous pairs, but they are not antonyms according to dictionary meanings. Heaven is in some religions, the place, or paradise sometimes envisioned to be in the sky, where God or the gods live and where

good people are believed to go after death, so that they can achieve perfect happiness.

The other way is any kind of other way. On this occasion, pragmatic impact is achieved again by pragmatic intention of exerting an emotional impact. In syntactic constructions made by the antithesis method, the object of opposition is the quality of the person, the subject mark, the behavior of the person or object.

For example: 1. Uning tetikligi, shahdam qadam tashlashi yosh bolaga chiqqan soqolday kishining kulgisini qistatar edi, lekin xop ozibdi, qorayibdi, shuni o'zi ham biladi ekan, shekilli oldini oldi... ("Asror bobo") 2. Yaxshi xat yozsa ham yig'laysan, yomon xat yozsa ham yig'laysan, nima qilaman ko'rsatib... ("Asror bobo") 3. Qishloqda hech kimning uyida pashsha yo'q, biznikida kechasi ham burun talashadi. ("Asror bobo") 4. Dehqonning uyi kuysa kuysin xo'kizi yo'qolmasin. Bir qop somon, o'n-o'n beshta xoda, bir arava qamish-uy, xo'kiz topish uchun necha zamonlar qozonni suvga tashlab qo'yish kerak bo'ladi. ("O'g'ri")

The personality traits are contentious, and the latter example relates with the quality

of the subject: a good letter, a bad letter. In the third and fourth sentences, actions and situations are met. Turobjon had two cups, and his wife could not even half a cup. In the example given, we can see the antithesis: Turobjon can eat two bowls and his wife cannot have half a cup. In this case, however, the formation of antibodies did not play a crucial role.

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